

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MODERN
SCIENCE AND SCIENTIFIC STUDIES

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Abstract: Among social issues, preservation of public health, reformation of the system of medical institutions, strengthening of emergency medical care, and training of medical personnel with modern knowledge became of special importance. In its activities, the Health Department of the city of Termiz has close ties with the American organizations Project Hope, Karelift International, Kauntepart International. In Uzbekistan, the most important factor in protecting human health has become the state policy of protecting the ecological environment and caring for the future of the young generation. In Uzbekistan, great practical work has been done in the field of education of the young generation, and special state programs have been developed and implemented in order to make our children healthy, physically strong, and increase their mental abilities and potential.

Keywords: medical care, public health, social issues, medical facilities, hospital, medical equipment, iodine deficiency.

In Uzbekistan, new socio-political changes have been implemented in the issue of public health. Among social issues, preservation of public health, reformation of the system of medical institutions, strengthening of emergency medical care, and training of medical personnel with modern knowledge became of special importance. As a result, since the early period of independence, a system of concrete reforms was implemented in the field of building specialized large treatment centers, finding funds for this, and forming family medicine networks.

During the USSR, little funds were allocated to the medical service of the Surkhan oasis, and no attention was paid to the construction of modern medicine. According to the state program, a 140-bed state emergency medical research center Termiz department was established in the region, and it was provided with the necessary medical and technical equipment. In its activities, the Health Department of the city of Termiz has close ties with the American organizations Project Hope, Karelift International, Kauntepart International.

In the cities of Karshi, Guzor, Shahrisabz, Mubarak, Koson of Uzbekistan, there are 9 hospitals, 395-doctor ambulatory-polyclinic institutions, ambulatory

and other medical institutions. 253 doctors and 823 secondary medical workers work in these medical institutions. According to the state program, the state emergency medical research center was established in the Karshi city department (220 places) and its units (410 places) under all district central hospitals and provided with the necessary medical and technical equipment.

A lot of work has been done to protect the health of urban residents, and new hospitals have been built and put into operation. Providing them with modern medical equipment has improved. Modern medical equipment was imported from abroad and installed. Existing hospitals in the cities were renovated, and the number of hospital beds increased to 3495. In particular, in 1991, 2 hospitals were operating in Boysun, 3 in Jarkurgan, 3 in Kumkurgan, 2 in Sherabad, and 4 in Shorchi. There were also 630 treatment places in the city of Denov, 420 in the city of Shorchi, 520 in the city of Sherabad, 530 in the city of Kumkurgan, 570 in the city of Jarkurgan, and 320 in the city of Boysun.

A number of positive changes and achievements have been achieved in the socio-economic and cultural spheres in Uzbekistan. It should be noted that significant works have been done in the cities of Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya in the southern regions of the republic. 13 hospitals, 3 sanatoriums, 63 ambulatory polyclinics, 72 treatment and prevention institutions serve the population in the cities of Kashkadarya. 200 highly qualified doctors and 2,700 medical workers with secondary education are working to protect the health of the population in treatment and prevention institutions. 5 billion in 2008-2010 alone. Medical equipment worth 525,000 soums was received. 5 billion 352 mln. Construction and repair works worth soums were carried out. 600 million to the cardiology center. modern medical equipment was installed.

In Uzbekistan, the most important factor in protecting human health has become the state policy of protecting the ecological environment and caring for the future of the young generation. Because, like the Republic of Khorezm and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the southern regions have become an ecologically dangerous area, and the harmful gases coming out of the aluminum plant of Tajikistan pose a serious threat to the health of the residents of the cities in the northern region of Surkhonadarya. According to experts in cities such as Denov, Shargun, Sho'rchi, and Sariosia, iodine deficiency in the living organism increases due to the fact that fluorine binds iodine to itself. Of course, this, in turn, leads to a violation of the functioning of the thyroid gland, and as a result, a number of diseases develop.

In particular, goiter, hypothyroidism and other diseases of the thyroid gland appear in these cities. As a result of the fluorine element binding to calcium, it causes a violation of calcium metabolism in the body and an increase in the size of the thyroid gland. As a result, due to the influence of the thyroid gland on the prostate gland, as a result of the production of a large amount of hormones, it causes a large amount of calcium element to leave the body, as a result of which bone fragility and osteoporosis appear. As a result of its excretion through the urine, many remain in the kidneys and lead to the formation of calcium stones. Taking the example of the cities of Denov and Saryosi, caries, fluorosis and oral cavity diseases have increased sharply, in addition to endocrine, urological, malignant neoplasms and complications of pregnant women before and after childbirth have increased year by year. For example, in the city of Denov, 4,996 endocrine diseases were observed in 2000, and in 2007, they reached 15,311. Endemic goiter among the population increased 6.2 times from 1992 to 2007, and in 6 months of 2008, this indicator was 111.8 per 10,000 population. Diseases of blood and blood production organs increased by 2.5 times (119.2 per 10,000 population in 1999, 252.2 in 2007), which increased sharply mainly among women of childbearing age.

In women, fetal stillbirths in the 2nd trimester increased between 2000 and 2007, and congenital anomalies among newborns increased by 15%. Among the oncological diseases recorded among the population, lymphomas, bone-joint connective tissue tumors have increased by 10-15%, stomach cancer has increased. Urinary tract diseases were 4,195 in 2000, by 2004 they were 6,984, and in 2007 this figure was 7,400. The number of malignant neoplasms increased from 107 in 2000 to 534 in 2004 and to 947 in 2007. This, in turn, shows the seriousness of the ecological situation in the northern part of the region. The number of disabled children aged 0-16 among the residents of Denov was 1007 at the end of 2000, 1295 in 2004, 1306 in 2005, and 1603 by the end of 2007. As a result of the negative impact of toxic waste on the environment during the work of the Tajikistan aluminum plant in the 1980s in the city of Sariosia, in 2000, the number of patients with goiter in the city was 3324, and the intensive index compared to the general population was 163.99, including 99.79 women. By 2004, the number of patients was 340, and the intensive rate was 199.26, gonorrhoea in women was 225, the intensive rate was 114.07. During 2007, the disease increased sharply, that is, 991 out of 1460 inhabitants suffered from various forms of goiter. In 2000, there were 240 cases of fluorosis, and in 2007, this number increased to 544. In 2000, 261 cases of

oral mucosal diseases were registered, and by 2007, this figure had increased to 603 cases, which means that the dynamics of various dental diseases is increasing year by year. Diseases of blood and blood production organs (anemia) were 288 in 2000, 725 in 2004, and 518 at the end of 2007. Respiratory diseases were 326 in 2000, by 2004 this number was 526, and by 2007 this number was 2061. An important international conference on preventing this situation was held on November 16-17, 2010 in Tashkent, where the world scientific community expressed their opinions.

In addition to the development of the medical system of the health departments of the cities, during the years of independence, the republic also achieved the development of various types of sports, the results of which are clearly visible in the tennis, wrestling and chess competitions held at the world level. Athletes of Uzbekistan have achieved high results of spiritual and physical fitness and revived ancient sports customs and traditions. Laws and decisions have been developed on the further development of sports, raising a healthy and mature generation. On January 14, 1992, at the 9th session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "On Physical Education and Sports" was adopted. On January 17, 1993, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted a special decision on measures to fundamentally improve the organizational foundations and principles of football development in Uzbekistan in order to further develop public and professional football in Uzbekistan, strengthen its material base, train and educate a new generation of football players, and increase the international prestige of the country's football. done In 1992, in the international wrestling competitions held in the southern cities, national wrestling was founded, and this sport was revived in memory of At-Tirmizi and in the name of the scholar. As a result, the national wrestling of the Uzbek people has become an international sport. This type of national wrestling is held every 2 years in southern cities.

In 1999, the indoor Tennis Palace and the National Wrestling Halls, which meet the requirements of international tennis, were built and put into operation. Based on the Decision No. 271 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 27, 1999 "On measures to further develop physical education and sports in Uzbekistan" and the comprehensive plan "Year of a Healthy Generation", a number of events were held in public education departments of cities. 2010, 234 students in city schools, 12,500 students in sports clubs are engaged in sports. For example, in the city of Termiz there are 2 stadiums, 8 football fields, 3 swimming pools, 2 tennis courts, 14 outdoor tennis

courts, 19 volleyball courts, 14 basketball courts, 10 handball courts, and other sports facilities. 8 sports schools in 17 sports are working in the city. More than 5,925 students regularly attend their classes. More than 27,000 people are engaged in physical culture and sports in the city, and more than 5,000 residents of the city participate in sports sections. This work is led by 200 professionals. It is gratifying that the competition dedicated to the memory of Hakim al-Termizi in the national form of wrestling and the international competitions in this type of sport for the prize of the President of Uzbekistan were held in Termiz for the first time. In 1999, the international tournament held in Termiz was given the name of Asia.

In Uzbekistan, great practical work has been done in the field of education of the young generation, and special state programs have been developed and implemented in order to make our children healthy, physically strong, and increase their mental abilities and potential. As a continuation of these works, 2014 was declared as the "Year of the Healthy Child" in our country. The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov emphasized this issue; "First of all, a healthy child is the result of a healthy and united family...Secondly, it is well known to all of us that the role and influence of the health care system in raising a healthy child is huge, and at the same time, it has a great responsibility...Thirdly, education and upbringing in raising a healthy child and the role and influence of sports should be further strengthened...Fourth, it is clear to all of us that raising our children, the new generation, to be healthy and mature, and achieving this goal, without a doubt, must be in the center of attention of our state and society, and must remain the priority direction of our policy. instructions are of particular importance. In Uzbekistan, in 2013, special positive things were done in terms of health care of our people, improvement of material and technical support of this field, new modern treatment, training and retraining of qualified specialists. In particular, the medical association in Chirakchi district of Kashkadarya region and the medical association in Sherabad district were newly built and equipped with modern medical equipment. In the Surkhandarya region, the multidisciplinary children's and adult medical center was completely reconstructed. The commissioning of 132 health facilities and 98 children's sports facilities in Kashkadarya region in 2001-2013 is serving to fundamentally change not only the appearance of cities and villages, but also the outlook and attitude of our people to life, strengthening their confidence in the future.

In 2009-2013, 40 health centers and 58 children's sports facilities were newly built and reconstructed in Surkhandarya region. In order to raise the young generation in a healthy and well-rounded way, in 2012-2013, 17 children's sports facilities, music and Art schools were built and provided to children with modern equipment.

In conclusion, it should be noted that in the process of scientific analysis of urbanization processes, it was justified that the cultural and spiritual image of cities changed radically due to independence as a result of the implemented reforms.

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